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From Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) To The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): Periscoping The Grassroots Development Policies In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the transition from the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and its impact on grassroots development in Anambra State. The study was quantitative in nature as data collection was based on the primary sources of data, while the structural functionalism theory was adopted as the analytic framework. The paper examined the MDGs/SGDs and grassroots development in Anambra State, using selected LGAs and communities that cut across the three senatorial districts in the State as the study area. The analysis of data and discussion of findings showed that the relationship between MDGs and grassroots development policies in Anambra State lies in the application of a general principle to a particular situation or the effort to practically substantiate or apply global policy objectives to a specific social level. Governments' effort to use local policies to achieve the MDGs/SDGs didn't quite succeed as could be seen from the indicators of development assessed in the study. The study recommended among others that the relationship between UN MDGs/SDGs and grassroots development in Anambra State lies in application of a general principle to a particular situation or in the effort to practically substantiate or apply global policy objectives to specific social level. Evidence from this study indicate that it didn't quite work out. It is therefore necessary for the government to make deliberate policies that will address the needs of the people comprehensively. Such local policies will take cognizance of some environmental issues and socio-cultural peculiarities which the MDGs may not have taken note of.

Keywords: Development, Goals, Grassroots, Millennium, Sustainable

INTRODUCTION

Grassroots development is a process where community groups come together to take collective action and generate solutions to common problems. It is the capacity of grassroots to organize themselves in order to improve lives, livelihoods, homes, assets, services, and infrastructure (Escandón, 2010; Okonjo-Iweala, 2012). This is where the people of a community plan their own projects and seek financial and technical support themselves (Ojo, 2014). It involves economic, social, environmental and cultural actions taken at the grassroots level that are closest to the ordinary citizen. It includes grassroots capacities to advance those development processes, social networks and institutional partnerships that strengthen its ability to anticipate, cope with, resist and recover from underdevelopment.

As the end period of MDGs, 2015, drew to a close, the United Nations felt that the gains of MDGs should not be allowed to fizzle away. Thus, came the proposal that after 2015, MDGs scheme therefore continued as Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). SDGs is to be a process of development in continuation of MDGs. United Nations (2015) stated that in the SDGs, the eight goals of MDGs are expanded to seventeen goals. Nations including Nigeria are participating in putting forward its recommendations for a new agenda in the SDGs. SDGs development agenda will pick up where the MDGs left off. But for any new agenda/framework to succeed, the remaining gaps left by the MDGs must be filled in order to eradicate poverty and hunger and promote sustained and inclusive economic growth, allowing people everywhere to thrive. It is important to evaluate exactly what the MDG effort has achieved so far in grassroots development.

A visit to the Millennium Project's website on the goals and what they have accomplished so far shows that while there is global progress, it was a slower journey than expected. Globally, the MDGs have undoubtedly been highly successful raising visibility, strengthening governments' commitments to poverty reduction, rallying the world behind a moral purpose, providing policy direction, setting out specific outcome indicators and catalyzing increased investments in several important areas and sustaining efforts to promote development. However numerous studies on the MDGs have revealed mixed failures and progress (Ahmed, 2013; Ezeobi, 2014; Jakimow, 2011; Nwanolue, Osegbo & Iwuoha, 2012; Gaiha, Imai & Arul, 2009; Sabou, 2015).

The progress made by MDGs for grassroots development in Anambra State has been sufficiently assessed in research. It was the expectation of the general public in the State that the implementation of MDGs was to be a panacea to all the problems facing grassroots development in Anambra State. One also believes that the State government would have provided all the financial requirements and support to actualize MDGs in the state. However, the high rate of poverty, gender inequality, child and maternal health, HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases, poor environmental sustainability, and lack of transparent international cooperation for grassroots development is source of concern to all. Upon the expiration of the MDGs, the United Nations (2015) states that the pendulum has shifted from MDGs to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The same pendulum shift is emerging in Anambra State from ANIDS to ASSEB. Equally as important to drafting a new development framework, is the need to assess the impact and effectiveness of the MDGs on the lives of people. For SDGs and ASSEB to progress more than MDGs, the question of assessing the impact of MDGs on grassroots development becomes critical. Therefore, against the background of the strategic position of grassroots development, as the chief driver for national development and credible change, and the need to avoid the mistakes of MDGs in the new SDGs, this research seeks to assess the impact of MDGs on grassroots development in Anambra State of Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

MDGs, SDGs and Grassroots Development Re-examined

The United Nations Millennium Declaration, signed in September 2000 commits world leaders to combat poverty, hunger, disease, illiteracy, environmental degradation, and discrimination against women. Their importance is highlighted by Biao (2008) who pointed out that the MDGs represent an extraordinary consensus by the international community on the nature of development and on a set of potentially achievable targets. According to World Bank (2010), in one sense they were not new because they had antecedents in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the Development Decade of the 1960s and the many United Nations (UN) summits in the second half of the 20th century that set goals for reducing hunger, improving health, eradicating diseases and educating children. Noting that the MDGs are not the first time that global promises have been made about eradicating or rapidly reducing human deprivation.

The concept of sustainable development (SD), according to Mensah and Casadevall (2019) and Ezeokoli et al. (2023), has been widely debated in theoretical importance in areas of social, policy, and academic circles over the years. Although the concept has gained prominence and is famous in theory it tends to be neglected in practice (Ezeokoli et al., 2023; Mensah & Casadevall, 2019). The report of the World

Commission on Environment and Development (WCED, 1987) defined SD as the development that meets the needs of the present without undermining the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. SD is an important concept in today's world and is accepted as the basis for measuring global development (Kioumarsis et al., 2022). The key goal of SD is to achieve environmental equilibrium, economic growth, and social progress (Gossling-Goldsmith, 2018; Zhai & Chang, 2019).

The meaning of the term 'grassroots' is also often clearly defined in a contrast with higher hierarchy levels, not only in a territorial perspective, but very often in the context of a certain organization's hierarchy. Weiping and Jiayi (2011) define the term 'grassroots' as the common or ordinary people in a country, rural regions, rural population, ordinary voters; who are not political office holders. Concurring with the above definitions, Mutisya and Yarime (2011) as well as Jakimow (2011) present grassroots as the local or ordinary people in the geographical point of view as distinct from the active leadership of a party or organization. The grassroots in this sense are seen as average villagers who have the desire, the right and the capability to promote their own welfare and prosperity and to participate in decisions that affect their lives. In essence, grassroots are the common people, especially as contrasted with or separable from the elite group.

Empirical Studies

Globally, numerous studies have been conducted on the MDGs and grassroots development. Some of these studies are presented in this section.

Brinkerhoff (2024) investigates the performance of Cooperate Social Reasonability (CSR) under the MDGs programme. The study conceptualizes Cooperate Social Reasonability (CSR) to include NGOs' activities. He recalled UNDP (2003) which states that MDGs should establish ambitious targets for promoting economic growth, improving health and education, empowering women, creating sustainable development and reducing poverty. He adds that government is not only to be seen as active actor in MDGs (and by extension in SDGs following post 2015), but should structure and influence the contributions of private businesses and NGOs. Brinkerhoff (2004) adds that what the government needs to do is to actively perform its activities under MDGs. It should then create enabling environment for private sector and NGOs to operate. He defines enabling environment as a set of interrelated conditions – such as legal, bureaucratic, fiscal, informational, political and cultural – that impact on the capacity of developmental actors to engage in development process in a sustained and effective manner.

In a related development, a paper by Bussolo and Medvedev (2017) summarizes the policy lessons from applications of the Maquette for MDG Simulations (MAMS) model to two low income countries: Ghana and Honduras. Results show that costs of MDGs achievement could reach 10-13 percent of GDP by 2015, although, given the observed low productivity in the provision of social services, significant savings may be realized by improving efficiency. Sources of financing also matter: foreign aid inflows can reduce international competitiveness through real exchange appreciation, while domestic financing can crowd out the private sector and slow poverty reduction. Spending a large share of a fixed budget on growth-enhancing infrastructure may mean sacrificing some human development, even if higher growth is usually associated with lower costs of social services. The pursuit of MDGs increases demand for skills: while this encourages higher educational attainments, in the short term this could lead to increased income inequality and a lower poverty elasticity of growth.

Another pertinent study was by Easterly (2007) which presented a critical assessment of how the millennium development goals are unfair to Africa. The author argues that a series of arbitrary choices made in defining "success" or "failure" as achieving numerical targets for the Millennium Development Goals made attainment of the MDGs less likely in Africa than in other regions even when its progress was in line with historical or contemporary experience of other regions. The author found that two-thirds reduction in child mortality is less likely when a continent stands at very high mortality rate, as Africa did. Africa was said to be failing the goal of reducing maternal mortality by two-thirds, but there was no data on maternal mortality trends. The author also noted that Africa was said to be failing to reduce HIV/AIDS, malaria, and TB prevalence, but there was no data on trends in these prevalence rates. Africa was relatively falling behind on reducing the percent without access to clean water, but it would have

been relatively catching up if it had been measured the conventional way of percent with access to clean water.

In a related development, Aavik (2007) in his thesis, examine discourses and policies aimed at engendering the UN Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). The thesis investigated gender mainstreaming into the MDGs by examining various influences to the UN in incorporating the dimension of gender into the MDGs as well as by considering feminist critique on the MDGs. In doing so, it conducted discourse and content analysis on UN policies and other documents. The thesis discovered that the gender dimension in the MDGs should rather be considered as a reductive reformulation of gender-related commitments adopted in international development conferences since the 1980s, and part of the UN's overall gender mainstreaming efforts, as opposed to involving substantial redefinitions or reorientations that would have emerged shortly before 2000. Further, the research suggests although the UN emphasizes the contribution of the civil society in influencing the preparation process of the MDGs, particularly relating to the inclusion of gender elements in the goals. Their major contribution has involved drawing explicit links between gender and various aspects of poverty and hence emphasizing the importance of considering the gender aspect in MDG-based strategies and policies aimed at alleviating poverty on local and national levels. In addition, the thesis concluded that the MDGs took as their basis the International Development Goals (IDGs), devised by the OECD in 1996, a fact which is not explicitly articulate in the background maternal to the MDGs published by the UN.

Bappenas (2010) whose study is also on Indonesia, said that success in achieving MDGs depends on the achievement of good governance, productive partnerships at all levels of the society. That study found that the government encourages companies to engage in Corporate Social Responsibility by providing tax exemptions in income tax and indirect taxes. She adds that the government sets the Road Map for achieving MDGs and gets the private sector to collaborate. This coordination and harmonization is very important so that CSR activities of private firms do not conflict with government projects or even other forms of activities. She further notes that funding is one of the known problems of MDGs. CSR have the potential of complementing government's efforts. According to her, when one takes a close look at the goals and aspirations of CSR and MDGs, there are indications that CSR can be harmonized with government's programmes to achieve the MDGs. Companies participation in fostering MDGs by implementing CSR will provide some benefits for the companies themselves. Some of such benefits are increased sales and market share, strengthened brand positioning, increased public image and increased profitability.

The literature captures the status of MDGs and grassroots development from the global perspective and the national perspective, the various organizations participating in this process. The literature reviewed examined the concept of grassroots, development and grassroots development. The Millennium development goals, its antecedents and critics were also reviewed. The review of related literature also explored the integration of the MGDs in Nigeria in general and Anambra state in particular. Finally, a review of empirical studies was presented. Attempts were made by many authors to capture the work being done towards accomplishment of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in many countries of the world including Kenya, Namibia, South Africa, Ghana and Nigeria. In all cases, there were mixed reports and findings, the overall effect of MDGS on grassroots development remains unclear. Moreover, in Nigeria, information and research about advancement towards the MDGs remains largely concentrated at the national level, the grassroots were largely ignored. In addition, the previous empirical studies in Nigeria were limited in analyzing few MDG indicators, relied heavily on naive projections and grassroots programme evaluation have been neglected. Whether the level of Anambra State advancement towards the Millennium Development Goals is inadequate for it to achieve the desired targets on the human development parameters by 2015 was not addressed in literature. Besides, none of the studies critically focused on assessing the MDGS and grassroots development by looking at the eight goals simultaneously and data on the status of MDGs in the state since inception was missing. Even the available claims on the effects of MDGs were mostly anecdotal reports from government and its agencies. The voices of the grassroots on the MDGS need to be heard as a way of assessing progress made. These are the gaps in

literature. These gaps need to be addressed and suggested for improvement made so that development will not again elude Anambra State in the post 2015 agenda. To fill these gaps and with the kind of disparities and contrasts that exist in the socio-economic fabric of various states, it seems but natural to have some studies and strategies concentrating on the existing position of states on the MDG parameters and their impact at the grassroots.

Theoretical Orientation

The theoretical framework of analysis in this study rests on the theory of the structural functionalism. DeRosso (2013), structural functionalism, or systems theory, functionalism is a theory that states that societies contain interdependent structure, each of which performs certain functions essential for societal maintenance. It is a framework for building theory that sees society as a complex system whose parts work together to promote solidarity and stability. This approach looks at society through a macro-level orientation, which is a broad focus on the social structures that shape society as a whole, and believes that society has evolved like organisms. This model of political analysis has been more widely used in the sphere of comparative politics because it provides for standard categories for different types of political system.

Functionalism presents a view of social world as essentially harmonious and stable for progressive change. According to Preston (1996), he used functional theory of action to analyze society and other general social system that comprises a set of subsystems that deals with various social sciences such as economics, sociology, politics and psychology. A further explanation by Ugwu and Bako (2014), presented structural-functionalism as a tradition of social analysis that sees society as a mosaic of functions and structures that perform them. For example, in order to survive, a society needs to reduce poverty, educate its children, produce goods, govern its affairs and provide security for its members. These are functions and they necessitate a number of structures such as institutions/agents, industries, parliaments, and so on.

In applying functionalism to this work, the activities of the state government on then MDGs and now SDGs in relation to their relative impacts on the grassroots are examined. The structural system is such that it is from the grassroots that the society and state emerge. Grassroots in Anambra State have physiological needs (reproduction, health, wealth, education, equality, food, shelter, etc) and the government as a political institution exists to meet these needs. Meeting these needs require institutional devices such as then MDGs and present SDGs. When the needs of individuals, who comprise society, are met, then the needs of society are met.

While MDGs was globally-enunciated development benchmarks, SDGs came with a more internationalizing agenda with global ambitions cannot produce on-the-ground change for ordinary citizens or grassroots communities without targeting the programmes at the grassroots. Country-level achievement of the 2015 and beyond with the introduction of SDGs depends on appropriate and effective policies and public spending by both national and sub-national government. By the constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria 1999, the responsibility for MDGs-related public services is shared among the federal, state and local governments. Notable among them are economic planning/management, agriculture, education, health and social welfare.

Given the constitutionally-assigned preoccupation of the federal (central) government with universal or international issues like defence, security, foreign affairs and macroeconomic policies, achieving MDGs in education at whatever level of government, MDGs should represent a balancing of several considerations geared towards transforming the lives of the grassroots people. This can be achieved through the MDGs targets if capital projects are appropriately implemented on projects that directly affect the grassroots. The MDG process can be hindered or accelerated depending on policy synergy and complementary programmes across the three tiers of government. Because Nigeria's states and local governments ideally should be the closest to the grassroots people, in terms of providing basic public services, their actions and inactions could impact greatly on MDGs. It is not enough to mobilize resources for the MDGs as claimed by State documents; the impact of the programmes and projects executed by

such resources is equally significant. The fact that resources are limited, government must be disciplined in its choices, scope, and implementation, if budgets are to make the desired impacts on the grassroots.

METHODOLOGY

The design considered most appropriate for the study is descriptive survey design. The choice of the design was largely informed by the fact that a part of the population (sample) would be studied for the purposes of generalizing the result for the entire population of interest.

This paper is to provide a critical assessment of the MDGS as well as its sister programme, SDGs towards grassroots development in Anambra State of Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the people of Anambra State. Administratively, the state has twenty-one (21) local government councils and three (3) senatorial districts of North, Central and South. Each senatorial district consists of seven (7) local government areas. Two local government areas were selected purposively from each senatorial district for the study. Purposive selection method was used to ensure that both rural and urban local government areas were reflected in the sample selection for the purposes of achieving balanced opinions from the respondents. By this estimation, 400 becomes the sample size for the study. Furthermore, the number of respondents allocated to each LGA selected for the study was determined through proportionate sampling method. Note that the LGAs included in the sample were purposively selected to reflect urban-rural divide for the needed balanced view to be achieved from the respondents.

The technique used in selecting the respondents within the communities was simple random sampling. This was achieved with the help of table of random numbers. It was considered appropriate to use a probability sampling design at this stage of selection because of the homogeneity that has been achieved in the population. The data for the study came from two main sources namely: primary and secondary sources.

The data generated in the study were analyzed using graphical presentation of the opinions of the respondents given from the interview schedule administered to some community leaders and the test of hypotheses.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

In this section, we presented and analyzed the demographic characteristics of the respondents, graphically presented and analyzed the results of the interview with the stakeholders in the communities, answered research question one by means of summary statistics and carried out the test of hypothesis for hypothesis one to ensure that the answers obtained in research question one did not occur by chance but rather, statistically relevant.

Demographic Features of the Respondents

In this section of the analysis, personal data of the respondents were analyzed and they include gender, marital status of the respondents, age bracket, highest qualification of the respondent, the length of time in years, that the respondents have lived in the current community and the main/primary occupation of the respondents at the time of the survey. The need to analyze these demographic characteristics of the respondents arose so that the suitability of the respondents for the study may be determined. The suitability is in terms of capacity and eligibility for discussing the issues surrounding the MDG projects and grassroots development in Anambra State.

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents by Gender

S/N	Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	Male	283	72.8	72.8	72.8
2.	Female	106	27.2	27.2	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The analysis in Table 1 shows that 283 respondents representing 72.8 percent of the sample are male while 27.2 percent are female, thus showing that the sample consists of more males than females.

Table 2: Marital Status of the Respondents

S/N	Marital Status	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	Married	247	63.5	63.5	63.5
2.	Single	88	22.6	22.6	86.1
3.	Widowed	15	3.9	3.9	90.0
4.	Separated	23	5.9	5.9	95.9
5.	Divorced	16	4.1	4.1	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 2 shows that 247 respondents representing 63.5 percent of the sample are married, 88 representing 22.6 percent are single, 3.9 percent are widowed, 23 representing 5.9 percent are separated and 16 representing 4.1 percent are divorced. The implication of analysis is that greater percentage of the respondents in the sample are in stable family units such that they are in the right frame of mind to discuss the issues under investigation.

Table 3: Distribution of the Respondents According to Age Bracket

S/N	Age Bracket (in years)	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	18-24	26	6.7	6.7	6.7
2.	25-34	77	19.8	19.8	26.5
3.	35-44	130	33.5	33.5	60.0
4.	45-54	83	21.3	21.3	81.3
5.	55 and above	73	18.7	18.7	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Apart from the distribution of age of the respondents presented in Table 3, estimation of the average age through the application of arithmetic mean calculation shows that the average age in the sample is 42 years thus indicating that the sample consists of people who are relatively young and as such ought to be active participants in any developmental efforts in the community.

Table 4: Distribution of the Sample by Highest Education Qualification

S/N	Highest Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	High School Certificate	107	27.5	27.5	27.5
2.	Poly/College of Education	135	34.6	34.6	62.1
3.	First Degree	109	28.1	28.1	90.2
4.	Higher Degree	22	5.7	4.7	95.9
5.	Other qualifications	16	4.1	4.1	100.0
	Total	389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

As could be seen from Table 4, 107 respondents representing 27.5 percent of the sample said they have high school certificate as their highest educational qualification, 135 of them representing about 34.6 percent said they have polytechnic or College of Education Certificate that is National Diploma (ND) or Higher National Diploma (HND) or National Certificate of Education (NCE). Also, 10.9 representing 28.1 percent of the respondents said they have first degree certificate, 22 representing 5.7 percent said they have higher degree certificate while 16 representing 4.1 percent said they have other qualifications which includes other professional certificates. The implication of the results is that the sample consists of people who are fairly literate and therefore were presumed to be capable of discussing all issues relating to MDGs and grassroots development in Anambra State.

Table 5: Distribution of the Respondents by Length of Time in the Community

S/N	Length of Time (in years)	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	0-5	22	5.7	5.7	5.7
2.	6-10	30	7.7	7.7	13.4
3.	11-15	140	36.0	36.0	49.4
4.	16 and above	197	50.6	50.6	100.0
Total		389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The analysis in Table 5 shows that more than 50 percent of the respondents have lived in their current communities for 16 years and more, 36 percent have lived for between 11 and 15 years, 7.7 percent have lived for between 6 and 10 years and 5.7 percent have lived in theirs for 5 years and below. It shows that greater proportion of the sample have lived long enough in their current communities to understand if any developmental projects executed by the MDG in collaboration with the government, has taken place within the period of the study.

Table 6: Distribution of the Respondents by Main/Primary Occupation

S/N	Occupation	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative
1.	Civil/Public Servant	65	16.7	16.7	16.7
2.	Trader	98	25.2	25.2	41.9
3.	Farmer	140	36.0	36.0	77.9
4.	Artisan	44	11.3	11.3	89.2
5.	Politician	30	7.7	7.7	96.9
5.	Retiree	12	3.1	3.1	100.0
Total		389	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

As could be seen from Table 6, 140 respondents representing 36 percent of the entire sample said their main or primary occupation is farming, 98 representing 25.2 percent said they are traders, 16.7 percent of them are either civil or public servant and 11.3 percent of them said they are artisans. Interestingly, 30 respondents representing 7.7 percent said their occupation is politics that is, they earn their living primarily from politics. The result as presented shows that government need to support farming activities in the areas of supply of improved seedlings, provision of herbicides, pesticides, fertilizer as well as extension workers services to teach farmers new techniques in farming methods among others. The implication is that any developmental policy coming from the government should recognize the chunk of those involved in agriculture for the policy to be effective and impact on the people.

Presence of MDG/SDG Projects in the Community

The community leaders were asked in this section to indicate whether there is presence of any MDG project in their communities and their responses are presented in the simple bar chart shown below.

Figure 1: Presence of MDG Projects in the Community

The figure above shows that overall, only 15 percent of the stakeholders interviewed said they have at least one developmental project from MDG/SDG in their communities, 25 percent said none, 10 percent said they do not know whether any exist or not and as much as 50 percent said that those located in their communities are either non-functional and dilapidated or in a very sorry state. Apart from the opinions given by the respondents, in the course of our questionnaire administration, those physical infrastructures such as water projects, road constructions/rehabilitation, toilet facilities, etc. that could be seen in the areas that we visited, were in very bad conditions thus negating the very essence of providing them to the people.

Community Response to MDG-Projects

We tried to find out here how the MDG/SDG developmental initiatives were received by the community leaders and the people and the level of cooperation given to them when it was first introduced. This was done with the understanding that such support is key to the success of any developmental efforts in that regard. It helped also to establish the level of hope the people have on MDG as an intervention that could lead to improved conditions of living for them.

Received with:

Figure 2: Reception of MDG-Projects in the six Focal LGAs used in the Study

The multiple bar chart in figure 2 above is the presentation of how the members of the communities within the LGAs received MDG/SDG projects in their constituent communities. The figure shows that in Ayamelum LGA, the people were enthusiastic about it as 50 percent says they received it with much hope. However, the situation is not the same in Onitsha North LGA where only 10 percent of the people said they received it with much hope and 55 percent said without hope. A close look at the figure shows obviously that rural based LGAs were of much hope that MDG projects would bring about improvement in their living conditions as could be seen from the ratings of the people of Ayamelum, Anaocha and Orumba North LGAs, unlike what obtains in Onitsha, Awka South and Nnewi North LGAs.

Specific Facility(s) Provided by MDG/SDG in the Locality

In this section, we sought to determine the particular project that MDG/SDG provided or supported its provision in the constituent communities of each local government area under investigation, with a view to ascertaining its effect on the lives of the beneficiaries. Their responses were not restricted to functioning projects or programmes only but any project/programme which was established by MDG or MDG-assisted.

Figure 3: Multiple Bar chart showing specific MDG/SDG projects in the Constituent Communities of the Focal LGAs.

As could be seen from the figure, only 10 percent said they have MDG water project sited in their communities in Ayamelum LGA. However, 30 percent and 40 percent in the LGA said there are health and educational service support projects. In Onitsha North LGA, 35 percent said there are skills acquisition centers provided by MDG, 40 percent in Anaocha LGA said they have educational service support projects while 35 percent said so in Awka South LGA. It is disheartening to note that there is complete absence of such skills acquisition center in Ayamelum and Orumba North LGAs. It is also very important to point out that both health and education services have received more intervention than any other social and economic indicators from the MDG and that more of them are from the urban based LGAs as the analysis in figure 4.3 has indicated. This, however, is irrespective of whether such projects/programmes are still on or have been abandoned.

Opinions on who should Decide the Project to be Executed in a Community

It became necessary to find out from the respondents whose responsibility it is to decided what services or programmes should be provided either by the government or development partners. This is because experience has shown that when the beneficiaries participate in deciding what should be provided for them based on their priority list, the project or service tend to be sustainable and also impact substantially

on the people as they usually take ownership of such project and provide the necessary protection required to make it achieve best results.

Figure 4: Opinion of the Stakeholders on who should decide what to Provide in the Community

Figure 4 presents stakeholders opinion on who should decide what to provide for the communities. As could be seen from the figure, the choice of the community as the decider of what to provide is very obvious across the LGAs except for Nnewi North LGA. For instance, in Ayamelum LGA, whereas 30 percent said the leadership of the town union should decide what to provide, 50 percent of them said it should be left for the members of the community to decide. Also, in Onitsha North LGA, 40 percent said it should be the community, in Anaocha and Awka South LGAs, 60 percent and 70 percent of the respondents respectively said the community is in a better position to decide what should be provided for them. The choice of the community as the decider of what project/programme to establish cuts across the focal LGAs under study, except for Nnewi North where as much as 60 percent of the stakeholders said it should be a joint decision approach.

By implication, what the people have opted for here is participatory approach to grassroots development which happens to be the current trend for community development in both the developing and advanced economies. The benefits of such approach are innumerable to both the government and the beneficiaries and some of them are that the projects/programmes would be protected thereby guaranteeing sustainability. The reason that abandoned projects or programmes litter everywhere is because the communities were not involved in the procurement and as such, they could not take ownership of the projects to protect and make them sustainable.

Opinions on Impact of MDG/SDG Project in the Community

Community leaders were asked to indicate in this section whether the presence of MDG projects in their communities had led to improved conditions of living among their people. Their responses are presented in a simple bar chart in figure 5 below:

Figure 5: Assessment of Impact of MDG Projects on the Communities.

As figure 5 has shown, 20 percent of the community leaders across the focal LGAs being studied said MDG has impacted on the lives of the people, 50 percent said no impacts has been made, 20 percent chose to be indifferent and 10 percent noted that there has been improvement partially. The presentation gives the impression that MDG has not led to the development of the grassroots. This is the opinion of the direct beneficiaries and the reason could be due to the fact that the projects under the initiative were not consistent with the developmental needs of the people. Again, the development underscores the need for the people to be carried along in any effort that is targeted at making life better for them.

Table 7: Relationship between MDGs-SDGs and Grassroots Development Policies in Anambra State

S/N	Items of the Questionnaire	Alternative Responses					Total
		SA	A	D	SD	UND	
1.	The goal of eradicating hunger and extreme poverty is in line with government's pro-poor policies e.g., FADAMA III, capital and equipment support and provision of revolving loans to farmer.	188 (48.3)	167 (42.9)	20 (5.1)	10 (2.3)	4 (1.0)	389 (100)
2.	Private public partnership initiative in employment generation is in agreement with poverty reduction strategy e.g. SA Builler Breweries Distill Bottling Plant at Ozubulu and Onitsha.	171 (44.0)	175 (45.0)	25 (6.4)	9 (2.3)	9 (2.3)	389 (100)
3.	The goal of achieving universal primary education of the MDG is well located in state government's efforts to increase enrolment, especially at primary school level. It is found in UBEP's free and unhindered access.	185 (47.6)	169 (43.4)	21 (5.4)	10 (2.3)	4 (1.0)	389 (100)
4.	The goal of gender equality and women empowerment is well spelt-out in SEEDs (2007) as expressed in laws governing employment opportunities to accomplish equity in human development efforts and income distribution of the local policy.	179 (46.0)	174 (44.7)	19 (4.9)	10 (2.3)	7 (1.8)	389 (100)
5.	The goals of reducing child mortality and improvement in maternal health as well as combating HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases are well expressed in the health vision for the state. It includes the building of over 177 primary health care centers in the state.	183 (47.0)	172 (44.2)	20 (5.1)	10 (2.3)	4 (1.0)	389 (100)
6.	Environmental sustainability is ensured when today's development does not compromise tomorrow's development. All developmental efforts this days are sustainable developments.	180 (46.3)	179 (46.0)	18 (4.6)	7 (1.8)	5 (1.3)	389 (100)
7.	Although not much impact has been witnessed in community development across the state, development strategies of the state are closely related to MDGs.	178 (45.8)	168 (43.2)	24 (6.2)	10 (2.3)	9 (2.3)	389 (100)

8.	The goal of developing global partnership is closely related to the international cooperation for development which could be found under ANIDS initiative. It involved establishment of projects and programmes by USAID to maximize agricultural revenue and key enterprises in targeted sites (Markets).	179 (46.0)	167 (42.9)	25 (6.4)	10 (2.3)	8 (2.1)	389 (100)
9.	Development of entrepreneurship, mobilization of local savings, linkages with bigger industries and encouragement of rural development are means of reducing poverty as envisaged by MDG I.	171 (44.0)	175 (45.0)	25 (6.4)	9 (2.3)	9 (2.3)	389 (100)
10.	The immunization coverage provided for pregnant mothers, adequate infant nutrition, provision of vitamin A supplement and exclusive breast feeding were initiated in the State towards the achievement of MDGs 4 & 5.	186 (47.8)	169 (43.4)	19 (4.9)	9 (2.3)	6 (1.5)	389 (100)
Total		1800	1715	216	94	65	389.0
Percentage of Total		(46.3)	(44.1)	(5.6)	(2.4)	(1.7)	(100)

Note: Figures in parenthesis are percentages

: (SA = Strongly agree; A = Agree; D = Disagree, SD = Strongly disagree and UND = Undecided)

Percentage analysis of the research question one presented in Table 4.7 above shows that on the average, 46.3 percent of the respondents strongly agreed with all the items, 44.1 percent merely agreed, 5.6 percent disagreed, 2.4 percent strongly disagreed while 1.7 percent of them had no opinion. Also, across the items, there are variations. For instance, whereas 48.3 percent and 42.9 percent of the respondents strongly agreed and merely agreed respectively with item 1, 44 percent and 45 percent did so respectively for item 2. Similarly, it could be seen from the table that whereas 4.9 percent and 2.3 percent of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively with item 4, 4.6 percent and 1.8 percent did so for item 6 respectively.

Test of Hypotheses

As a tentative answer to the problem of the research under investigation and an answer which has no evidence supporting it until a full investigation is carried out, the hypotheses formulated to guide the study were tested. The main objective of hypothesis is to provide a starting point for investigating a research problem and at the same time to direct and adequately guide the investigation, with the intention of ensuring that the research does not deviate from the purpose of the study (Akuezilo and Agu, 2007). In the light of the above, all hypotheses constructed to strengthen the analysis were verified at 0.05 level of significance and 36 degrees of freedom through the application of an inferential statistical (Chi-square (χ^2)) test of independence).

Table 8: Summary of Chi-square (χ^2) Result for Hypothesis I

Hypothesis	Sample Size (n)	Degrees of freedom (df)	Chi-Square (χ^2) Values		Sig. Level (α)	Decision rule
			$\chi^2_{cal.}$	$\chi^2_{crit.}$		
I	400	36	29.611	43.773	0.05	Accepted

Note: $\chi^2_{cal.}$ means the value of χ^2 calculated and $\chi^2_{crit.}$ means the critical value of χ^2 .

Decision Rule I:

At 0.05 level of significance and 36 degrees of freedom, the calculated value of χ^2 (29.611) is less than the critical value of χ^2 (43.773) (see Appendix II for the details of estimation). Consequently, the alternative hypothesis was rejected while the null which suggests that the relationship between the MDGs/SDGs and grassroots development policies in Anambra State lies in the application of general principle to a particular solution was accepted.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The paper examined the MDGs/SGDs and grassroots development in Anambra State, using selected LGAs and communities that cut across the three senatorial districts in the State as the study area. The analysis of data and discussion of findings showed that the relationship between MDGs and grassroots development policies in Anambra State lies in the application of a general principle to a particular situation or the effort to practically substantiate or apply global policy objectives to a specific social level. Governments' effort to use local policies to achieve the MDGs/SGDs didn't quite succeed as could be seen from the indicators of development assessed in the study.

From the results of the analysis of data and the discussion of findings, summary and conclusion, we make the following recommendations:

1. The relationship between UN MDGs/SDGs and grassroots development in Anambra State lies in application of a general principle to a particular situation or in the effort to practically substantiate or apply global policy objectives to specific social level. Evidence from this study indicate that it didn't quite work out. It is therefore necessary for the government to make deliberate policies that will address the needs of the people comprehensively. Such local policies will take cognizance of some environmental issues and socio-cultural peculiarities which the MDGs may not have taken note of.
2. The MDG/SDG projects/programmes' implementation did not quite agree with the development needs of the grassroots in Anambra State. This explains why the communities (rural areas) have remain largely underdeveloped. Secondly, projects execution were not made in consultation with the community members and as such embezzlement as well as project abandonment became the order rather exception. The government or development practitioners should partner with the community stakeholders or leaders to identify their immediate priority to achieve effective results. There is also the need for the government to develop a mechanism for supervising, monitoring and evaluating on-going projects/ programmes so that situation reports can be given to ensure accountability and transparency in government dealings with the public.

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